
THE USE OF MODERN GEODETIC TOOLS IN THE CONSTRUCTION AND EXPLORATION OF BRIDGE CROSSINGS

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Abstract: The article highlights the specific features of the design of bridge crossings. The concept of a "bridge crossing" as an engineering structure is considered. The main stages of bridge crossing surveys and the reasons complicating their design are given. The methods of satellite measurements and satellite navigation systems for the design and operation of engineering buildings and structures are considered.

Key words: bridge, bridge crossing, satellite navigation systems, GLONASS, GPS.

The bridge is a very complex engineering structure. The design and construction of such an object is always a creative and responsible business. And it begins with choosing the location of the future bridge and the complex of geodetic works.

Modern bridge crossings are complex engineering structures, the main structural elements of which are bridge supports and superstructures.

During the construction of a bridge crossing on the ground, the position of the centers of bridge supports and other bridge elements is determined and fixed, as well as a detailed breakdown is performed during the construction of supports and the installation of superstructures.

For these purposes, a special geodetic marking network is being built, which ensures the execution of marking works at all stages of bridge construction. In addition, a rationally located and securely fixed center network can also serve as a basis for observing deformations of the bridge during its construction and operation [3].

A bridge crossing is a part of a highway, which is a complex of engineering structures consisting of a bridge crossing the watercourse itself; approaches to the

bridge — embankments with reinforced slopes, periodically flooded with water in floods; regulatory and protective structures designed to protect the bridge and approaches from the harmful effects of the water flow.

The bridge and the approaches to it are the main transport structures through which traffic flows are carried out. Regulatory and protective auxiliary structures are an integral part of the bridge crossing, without which in most cases it is impossible to ensure the safety and normal operation of the main crossing structures [5].

Geological surveys, topographic surveys and other types of research provide complete information about the types and composition of soils and the terrain where the construction of the facility is planned.

One of the main types of information about the area necessary for the development of bridge crossing projects is the materials of engineering and geodetic surveys. The composition of survey work, the scale, accuracy and volume of topographic surveys largely depend on the design stage (FS- feasibility study, EP - engineering project, WD — working documentation or WD — working draft) [5].

However, in accordance with the list of engineering tasks to be solved in the design of bridge crossings, the following types of basic work are performed during surveys for any stage of design in one volume or another:

- **engineering and geodetic works;**
- **hydrological surveys;**
- **hydrometric work;**
- **engineering and geological works;**

other work related to surveys for the design of bridge crossings in conditions of interaction with other hydraulic structures, the establishment of conditions for navigation and logging, etc.

It should be noted that all the listed main types of survey work are carried out with the mandatory use of geodesy methods. To carry out survey work, specialized parties (expeditions) are created, equipped with the necessary geodetic instruments and other equipment.

Surveys of bridge crossings are carried out in three stages: preparatory, field and desk [5].

Any geodetic work in construction is carried out taking into account the dimensions of structures and climatic conditions of a particular region. This allows us to identify the degree of man-made risks, the occurrence of which is associated with the influence of natural environmental factors, and to develop a set of engineering and protective measures.

Creation of a center network for geodetic support, a geodetic center network is created. Such a system plays a particularly useful role at all stages of the construction of bridges for various purposes. A special center base, which is formed in the right

way, is actively used in the future to monitor the deformation processes that may occur at various stages of construction of a complex engineering structure.

Also, surveyors can use other different forms when building center networks. The most commonly accepted and understandable scheme of a center network is the use of a shape that is bounded by two rectangles. It includes the axis of the bridge crossing and creates two main bases to carry out the breakdown of the supports with fixed serifs.

The level of traditional technologies for the production of topographic and geodetic works currently does not significantly meet the modern requirements of engineering surveys and computer-aided design in terms of volume, timing and cost of work, requirements for engineering and geodetic support of construction processes and operation of engineering structures, and finally, does not correspond to the modern level of development of automation and computer technology.

Currently, satellite geodetic receivers are widely used in geodetic production. Their main purpose is to accurately determine the increments of geocentric coordinates. When performing field measurements, the receivers use radio signals from the GLONASS satellite navigation systems (Russia) and NAVSTAR (USA). The use of satellite geodetic receivers for geodetic support of surveys, construction and operation of engineering structures provides higher accuracy and higher productivity than traditionally used geodetic technologies.

Satellite navigation systems, created for the first time in the USA — NAVSTAR and in Russia — GLONASS (Global Navigation Satellite System), have entered the international practice of solving military, navigation, engineering and other problems under the name "Global Positioning System" ("GPS") or literally — Global Positioning System.

Therefore, in the future, Satellite Navigation Systems (SNS) will be called using the international abbreviation ("GPS").

The ability to quickly determine the coordinates of a location is so essential in the life of modern humanity that GPS systems are considered as a "New asset of civilization." The appearance of satellite navigation systems, which have already become available to the average user, will certainly determine in the near future a qualitative change in the content and methods of production of most types of engineering and geodetic works [5].

The construction of bridges, as well as the construction of any other structures, requires the creation of a reference geodetic network. Using geodetic support networks, determine and fix the position of the centers of bridge supports and other bridge elements, make a detailed breakdown during the construction of supports and installation of superstructures, as well as monitor deformations of structures.

The geodetic network during the construction of bridges should be created in a single coordinate system and have increased accuracy in determining the coordinates of points. The points of the geodetic network that ensure the construction of this object as a single structure must physically exist during the construction of the object. This requirement is not easily feasible, since during the construction part of the points of the geodetic network is destroyed or violated.

Since the advent of the GLONASS and GPS satellite navigation systems, as well as on the basis of a continuous process of improving satellite measurement technology, the problems of creating geodetic reference networks have been solved on a qualitatively new basis. The development of highly efficient satellite methods of coordinate determination based on the use of global navigation systems fundamentally changes the technology and accuracy of determining geodetic coordinates and the principles of building geodetic networks. Based on the results of satellite measurements, the exact values of the coordinates are simultaneously determined both in terms of plan and height. Therefore, modern satellite methods of coordinate determination based on the use of global navigation systems GPS and GLONASS create conditions for the creation of a planned and high-altitude basis in the form of a single set of geodetic points.

Today, this problem is being successfully solved using satellite measurements. Their advantages are as follows:

- the ability to carry out geodetic measurements without eye contact between points at a distance of several thousand kilometers;
- taking measurements does not depend on weather conditions and time of day;
- increase the accuracy of measurements by reducing the influence of the atmosphere;
- measurements can be carried out in motion;
- monitoring of possible deformations in structures or in the Earth's crust;
- ultra-precise determination of all three coordinates of the object;
- automation of measurements increases labor productivity and minimizes errors.

The technique of satellite measurements consists in determining the distance from the receiver of the navigation system (GPS/GLONASS) to the satellite. The received data is adjusted, taking into account the amendments. Satellite measurements are carried out in two modes:

- static methods (receivers are motionlessly located at points whose coordinates are known, and at predetermined points; these methods are more accurate, but long-lasting);

- kinematic methods (less accurate, but faster; assume two receivers – one stands in place with known coordinates, and the other moves from point to point; a modem is installed on both receivers, which allows real-time use of kinematics mode).

The first group of methods are used in the construction of geodetic networks, and the second – in topographic surveying and surveying.

To date, satellite **measurement methods** are often used in such engineering and geodetic works as design, operation of engineering buildings and structures, cadastral surveys, surveys for topographic purposes, and so on.

References:

1. Вшивкова О. В. О комплексном подходе к решению рефракционной проблемы // Изв. вузов. Геодезия и аэрофотосъемка. – 2005. – № 4. – С. 41–46.
2. Карпик А. П., Мурзинцев П. П., Падве В. А. Прикладная геодезия. Геодезическое обеспечение изысканий, строительства и мониторинга мостовых сооружений : учеб. пособие. – Новосибирск : СГУГиТ, 2015. – 222 с.
3. Е. Б. Ключин, М.И.Киселев, Д.Ш.Михелев, В.Д.Фельдман; Под ред. Д. Ш. Михелева. Инженерная геодезия: Учебник для вузов — 4-е изд., испр. — М.: Издательский центр. «Академия», 2004. — 480 с. ISBN 5-7695-1524-4
4. В.А.Коугия, В.В.Грузинов, О.Н.Малковский и др. Геодезические работы при строительстве мостов. — М.: Недра, 1986.
5. Федотов Г. А. ИНЖЕНЕРНАЯ ГЕОДЕЗИЯ Учебник. — 2-е изд., исправл.— М : Высш. шк., 2004. — 463 с
6. <https://www.studmed.ru/>
7. <http://lib.sgugit.ru/wp/>